

PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

SOME MEDICINAL PLANTS USED IN SKIN PROTECTION

Mammadova Aytakin,

Assistant of Pharmacy department, Azerbaijan State Agricultural University

Nagiyeva Mahruh,

Head of Pharmacy department, Azerbaijan State Agricultural University

Tagiyeva Narmin,

Senior teacher of Pharmacy department, Azerbaijan State Agricultural University

Hasanova Lala,

Assistant of department of Anatomy, Pathological Anatomy and Pathological Physiology, Azerbaijan State Agricultural University

Cabrayilova Gunel

Assistant of Pharmacy department, Azerbaijan State Agricultural University

Abstract

Cosmetics are witnessing an increasing demand in the global market and represent a valuable natural gift. Herbal formulations have consistently garnered significant attention due to their potent efficacy and notably fewer or absent side effects compared to synthetic medications. The utilization of herbs and spices has been deeply rooted in the practice of preserving and enhancing human beauty since ancient times. In this study, we examined coconut oil, aloe vera, calendula, turmeric, green tea and sunflower oil plants.

Keywords: dry skin, skin protection, medicinal plants, cosmetics

Introduction

Women are known to prioritize beauty, prompting the utilization of diverse herbal beauty products to exude charm and youthfulness. Herbal cosmetics are experiencing a rise in demand worldwide, constituting a precious offering bestowed by nature. The efficacy of herbal formulations has long captivated considerable interest owing to their potent activity and relatively minimal adverse effects compared to synthetic drugs. The historical use of herbs and spices for beauty enhancement has been a longstanding tradition.

In the contemporary landscape, there is a growing trend within the pharmaceutical industry towards personal care products containing plant-derived ingredients. Cosmetic products integrating plant materials as active components fall under the category of cosmeceuticals. The escalating use of plant extracts in cosmetic concoctions can be attributed to the tarnished reputation of animal-derived extracts in recent years.

Natural compounds derived from plant extracts present a promising avenue for further exploration. However, plant extracts often lack clear definition regarding extraction methods, plant-to-solvent ratios, and active ingredient concentrations. Additionally, concerns regarding the stability of color, scent, transparency, and/or active components over time frequently pose limitations. Plant extracts differ from purified therapeutic agents in several aspects, primarily due to their dilute nature and the presence of various active principles (1).

Dry skin, characterized by a rough, scaly, cracked, and fissured surface, is commonly associated with persistent itch sensations, particularly chronic itch. Chronic itch accompanied by dry skin represents a prevalent clinical presentation in dermatological conditions like xerosis, atopic dermatitis, and psoriasis, as

well as in systemic diseases such as chronic kidney disease, chronic liver ailments, and diabetes mellitus (2).

When addressing dry skin concerns, coconut oil, aloe, and sunflower oil emerge as primary treatment options. Derived from the fruit or seed of the coconut palm tree (*Cocos nucifera*, family *Areaceae*), coconut oil boasts a melting point of 24 to 25 °C, allowing for easy utilization in both liquid and solid forms, commonly employed in culinary practices. Notably, coconut oil serves as an effective skin moisturizer and emollient, as demonstrated in studies showcasing its safety and efficacy as a moisturizing agent without adverse reactions. Furthermore, research highlights coconut oil's efficacy in preventing protein loss during hair combing and its traditional application in moisturizing and treating skin infections (3).

Traditionally, *coconut oil* has been utilized for the purpose of moisturizing and addressing skin infections. The emollient properties of coconut oil have been effectively showcased in patients with atopic dermatitis, highlighting its efficacy as a potent natural emollient for managing xerosis (3).

Derived from *Helianthus annuus* of the *Asteraceae* family, sunflower oil is a non-volatile oil extracted from sunflower seeds. This oil is rich in lecithin, tocopherols, carotenoids, and waxes. Within the realm of cosmetics, sunflower oil is recognized for its smoothing attributes and noncomedogenic nature. It aids in maintaining the integrity of the stratum corneum, while promoting hydration in the skin barrier, without inducing erythema (4).

Sunflower seed oil is notably abundant in linoleic acid and has been administered topically to treat essential fatty-acid deficiency due to its exceptional transcutaneous absorption, swiftly ameliorating the condition. Locally, these essential fatty acids play a crucial role in upholding the skin barrier and reducing

transepidermal water loss, which are pivotal considerations in addressing conditions like atopic dermatitis. There is a prevailing notion that formulations with higher concentrations of linoleic acid as opposed to oleic acid may offer enhanced benefits in this regard, with some clinical evidence supporting this contention (5).

Aloe vera is extensively used both internally and externally in human applications as a form of folk or alternative medicine. Renowned for its medicinal and cosmetic attributes, the *Aloe* species yields two key substances - a transparent gel and a yellow latex - that are harnessed in the production of commercial goods. Commonly, *Aloe* gel is integrated into topical medications designed for various skin conditions such as burns, wounds, frostbite, rashes, psoriasis, cold sores, and dry skin (6).

In the realm of cosmetics, *Aloe vera* is a prevalent ingredient due to its skin healing, moisturizing, and softening properties. By easily extracting the soothing gel from one of the *aloe vera* leaves, individuals can access its benefits. *Aloe vera* gel features prominently in numerous skin lotions, sunscreens, and cosmetic products. The application of *Aloe vera* is associated with wound and burn healing, insect sting alleviation, mitigating skin inflammation, possessing anti-inflammatory, antiseptic, antimicrobial, antitumor, anti-skin protection, anti-diabetic, antibacterial, anti-viral properties, all of which are pivotal for facilitating wound recovery (7).

The primary biologically active compounds found in *Aloe vera* encompass alkaloids, amino acids, anthraquinones, enzymes, phytohormones, flavonoids, tannins, organic acids, mineral salts, sterols, triterpenes, tannins, carbohydrates, and vitamins.

In the sphere of nutricosmetics, the juice derived from *aloe* leaves harbors a plethora of active constituents that boast antibacterial, antioxidant, anti-allergic, and anti-inflammatory attributes. These compounds play a role in fortifying skin blood vessels and the protective hydro-lipid barrier of the skin. Moreover, they enhance cellular metabolism by stimulating collagen synthesis from fibroblasts, thereby offering a spectrum of beneficial effects (8, 9).

Antioxidants, such as vitamins like vitamin C and vitamin E, flavonoids, and phenolic acids, have a significant role in combatting free radical species, which are the primary cause of various detrimental changes in the skin. While individual plant compounds show promise in skin protection, whole herbal extracts exhibit greater potential due to their intricate composition. The utilization of herbs in both medicine and cosmetics dates back centuries, with their well-established ability to address various skin conditions and enhance skin aesthetics. Given that ultraviolet radiation can lead to sunburns, wrinkles, reduced immunity to infections, premature aging, and cancer, there is a continuous necessity for shielding against UV radiation and mitigating its adverse impacts. Herbs and herbal formulations boast considerable potential owing to their antioxidant properties, as highlighted by numerous studies demonstrating the beneficial effects of green and black tea in ameliorating skin reactions post-UV exposure (10).

Antioxidants, whether exogenous or endogenous, synthetic or natural, can effectively prevent the formation of free radicals by either scavenging them or facilitating their breakdown, thus suppressing associated disorders. Presently, there is a surging interest in natural antioxidants derived from herbal sources. Epidemiological and in vitro investigations on medicinal plants and vegetables strongly support the notion that plant constituents with antioxidant properties can offer protective effects against oxidative stress in biological systems. The formation of free radicals is naturally regulated by a diverse array of beneficial compounds known as antioxidants. Apart from fruits and vegetables, herbs that may not have specific nutritional value can also serve as crucial sources of antioxidants. Notably, the leaves of black and green tea (*Camellia sinensis*), historically consumed by Western and Asian populations, respectively, represent a significant source of health-promoting antioxidants and are globally recognized as a prevalent form of daily herbal consumption (11).

Green tea, produced solely from the leaves of *Camellia sinensis* of the *Theaceae* family, emerges as a premier skin protectant, whether applied topically or ingested as a beverage or dietary supplement. Studies suggest that the catechins present in green tea exhibit antioxidant capabilities approximately 20 times more potent than vitamin E. It is imperative for individuals of all ages and genders to leverage this potent shield against the damaging effects of solar exposure.

The skin-regenerative effects attributed to green tea phytocomplexes, such as the stimulation of elastin and fibronectin production, regulation of collagen synthesis, and enhancement of local blood circulation, have been documented (11).

Calendula, also known as pot marigold, represents a genus encompassing approximately 12–20 species of herbaceous plants, either annual or perennial, within the *Asteraceae* family. The application of *Calendula* in suspension or tincture form serves to address various skin conditions such as acne, inflammation reduction, hemostasis, and tissue soothing.

Belonging to the *Asteraceae* family, *Calendula officinalis* L. originates from Central Europe and the Mediterranean region. Its flower oil, a prominent component in cosmetic formulations, comprises diverse bioactive elements like terpenoids, terpenes (particularly bisabolol, faradiol, chamazulene, arnidiol, and esters), carotenoids (primarily rubixanthin and lycopene structures), flavonoids (especially quercetin, isorhamnetin, and kaempferol aglycones), and polyunsaturated fatty acids (mainly calendic acid). Since the twelfth century, *Calendula officinalis* L. has been utilized for medicinal purposes, showcasing various biological effects such as angiogenic, analgesic, antimicrobial, antioxidant, and immunomodulatory properties. Its incorporation in cosmetic items is particularly prevalent in formulations designed for sensitive skin, offering a range of products for skin, eye, hair, and bath care, with established safety for cosmetic applications (12).

Turmeric, scientifically known as *Curcuma longa*, represents a rhizomatous perennial herbaceous plant from the *Zingiberaceae* family. Traditionally, women use turmeric on their cheeks to attain a natural golden

hue. In recent times, substantial attention has been directed towards curcumin, an isolated compound from turmeric, which serves as a coloring and flavoring agent, with a historical application in medicine. The multifaceted biological attributes of curcumin, coupled

with its non-toxic nature even at higher dosages, make it an attractive candidate for exploring therapeutic interventions in conditions such as skin tumors, colonic disorders, pancreatic ailments and various dermatological issues (Table 1.)

Table 1.

Medicinal plants and their chemical content

Medicinal plants	Chemical content	Part
Coconut oil	fatty acids, caprylic acid, capric acid, lauric acid, myristic acid, palmitic acid, stearic acid, oleic acid and linoleic acid	fruit
Aloe vera	chromone and anthraquinone, phenylpyrone derivatives, flavonoids, phenylpropanoids, coumarins, phytosterols, naphthalene analogs, lipids, and vitamins	leaves
Sunflower oil	linoleic acid, oleic, palmitic and stearic acids	seeds
Calendula	flavonoids, triterpenoids, glycosides, saponins, carotenoids, volatile oil, amino acids, steroids, sterols, and quinines	flowers
Tumeric	gallic acid, protocatechuic acid, epicatechin, rutin, curcumin, myricetin, and cinnamic acid	roots
Green tea	catechin, (-)-epicatechin, (-)-epicatechin 3-gallate, (-)-epigallocatechin and (-)-epigallocatechin gallate	leaves

Curcumin's protective mechanisms involve scavenging free radicals, mitigating inflammation through nuclear factor-KB inhibition, accelerating wound-healing processes, enhancing collagen deposition, and promoting fibroblast and vascular density in wounds, thereby improving both normal and impaired wound repair. Furthermore, curcumin exhibits a positive impact as a proangiogenic agent during wound-healing by stimulating transforming growth factor-beta, which facilitates angiogenesis and extracellular matrix accumulation, crucial for the wound repair's remodeling phase (13). Natural ingredients are everywhere and are continually gaining popularity, and the use of plant extracts in cosmetic formulation is on the rise. A cosmetic formulation including active principles of natural origin can protect the skin against exogenous or endogenous harmful agents, and help to remedy many skin conditions. In the future, it is possible that many new plants, extracts and oils of commercial significance will be identified, and many ethnobotanical uses and claims of many widespread herbs will be proven, new isolation and extraction techniques will be shown to give higher quality products.

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